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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

D7.1 Digital PV passport and marketplace defined

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
DBP	Digital Battery Passport
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EN50380	European Standard EN 50380:2017-09 for Marking and Documentation Requirements for Photovoltaic Modules
EV	Electro vehicle
EU	European Union
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
JRC	Joint Research Center
Minespider Platform	Blockchain backed online platform for digital product passports established and operated by Minespider GmbH
MNS	Minespider GmbH
PV	Photovoltaic
PV DPP	Digital Product Passport specifically designed for photovoltaic modules
PV Module	Photovoltaic Module

1. Executive summary

This report summarises a concept and the methodologies for a proposed marketplace that is backed by digital product passports (“DPP”) designed for photovoltaic modules (“PV Module”) and the related industry to meet the regulatory requirements as well as the expectations of the industry and the customers along the life cycle of a PV Module.

In particular a photovoltaic centric DPP (“PV DPP”) is presented that contains the essential information about the PV Module in order to enable and facilitate, in particular, efficient procurement and use, reuse, reprocessing or dismantling and recycling of PV Modules. The suggested content of the PV DPP is mainly focusing on the datapoints addressed by the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) as well as the European Standard EN 50380:2017-09 for Marking and Documentation Requirements for Photovoltaic Modules.

Moreover, a concept for a marketplace for the PV industry is outlined and visualized that can be expected to meet the common expectations of an easy to use online marketplace. It provides a PV industry focused online market not only for used PV modules and other PV related product offers but also product requests as well as service offers and requests. And it includes the common features and functionalities that enables a user to draft, edit and publish product or service listings and to filter and search for listings according to your needs. And a key element of this market place is that product offers can refer to and be backed by the respective PV DPPs as well as any other type of DPP generated on the blockchain-based Minespider Infrastructure.

2. Introduction

In order to have full traceability of PV waste in the future, PV DPPs are proposed. Accordingly the objective in this WP 7 and the respective Deliverable 7.1 is to conceptualise the PV DPP and its associated Marketplace.

MNS analysed and identified the relevant data needs and developed the respective data models, designs, concepts, workflows. This WP 7 touches on all areas of the PV development from supply chain, materials, design, manufacture and right through to EOL options.

As described in Task 7.1 (PV Passport Information Gathering), in a first step MNS explored and analysed the informational requirements and needs of the PV industry. This analysis included desktop research as well as interviews of project participants and other relevant stakeholders in the PV industry.

In a second step, as specified in Task 7.2 (Concept model for PV Digital Product Passports), MNS determined the concepts, workflows, and models to collect and share data along the supply chain for dismantling PV Modules, e.g. composition, H&S data, confidentiality aspects, consideration of the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (“ESPR”). MNS identified the data points, needs, and workflows that participants will need to operate a Digital Product Passport (DPP) system.

In a third step, as described in Task 7.3 (Blockchain Data Template), the design of blockchain-based data collection template has been determined and the way each project partner should interact with the blockchain-based tools, data security needs, and how this process can scale and interact with the wider industry. The full process chain has been considered to meet the requirements of applicable EU regulations, such as on ecodesign and DPPs.

In a fourth step, in accordance with Task 7.4 (Marketplace Concept Design) MNS developed user stories and concepts for the design of the online marketplace (up to MVP level) that shall be backed by the respective DPPs and linked to the Minespider Platform. This builds on DPPs, the PV modules and components as well as related services users intend to supply or procure. Accordingly, MNS (with input from other relevant partners) determined the concepts, workflows, and templates of an online marketplace that builds on the blockchain-based MNS infrastructure to collect and share data along the supply chain that is of relevance for sellers, buyers and related services providers, in particular for an efficient procurement and use, reuse, remanufacture or recycling and dismantling of PV modules and components. MNS identified the relevant data points, needs, and workflows that the participants need to operate within the marketplace. The design of the blockchain-based online marketplace has been determined as well as the way each user needs to interact with the MNS tools, data security needs, and how this marketplace can scale and interact with the wider industry in the future and to improve efficiencies in decision making and further processing in the marketplace.

Acknowledgement: This project builds on learnings from and standard methodologies already developed in the MINESPIDER Project (Grant Agreement number: 946437), the BATRAW Project (Grant Agreement number: 101058359), as well as the RECIRCULATE Project (Grant Agreement number: 101103972) following EU recommendations. In view of the specific needs of the PV industry, the learnings and methodologies have been considered, reasonably adapted and ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for the APOLLO Project (Grant Agreement number: 101122277).

The overall goal is to create user-friendly, reasonably homogeneous and practical tools and within online environments that can be extended to and implemented for various types of products and industries along the respective supply chains and product life cycles.

In the following chapter the PV DPP conceptualisation will be described in more detail, which then leads to the chapter that describes the concept of the PV centric online marketplace that will be backed by DPPs in order to facilitate transparency, traceability and sustainability along the PV Module's life cycle.

3. PV DPP Information of Relevance

In the context of the APOLLO Project, MNS explored and analyzed the informational requirements and needs of the PV industry. Whereas in Europe, the major driver in terms of digital product passports is the European Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulations (ESPR). Also the EU Regulation 2023/1542 of 12 July 2023 concerning batteries and waste batteries, (EUBR), which was published earlier than the ESPR and includes detailed stipulations on digital battery passports (DBP), is expected to have a considerable impact on other types of DPPs, too.

Moreover, at this date, the main standard in terms of PV Modules is the European Standard EN 50380:2017-09 for Marking and Documentation Requirements for Photovoltaic Modules (EN50380).

In the following, the results of the analysis of the European Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulations (ESPR) as well as the EN50380, will be presented. Following a very short introduction into ESPR and the EN50380, the results are presented in the form of tables that describe the suggested type, unit and/or format of data to be collected/provided as well as comments or references to understand the reasoning for the respective suggestion.

Moreover, DPP related standards like the CIRPASS Project (which identified 375+ Standards of relevance), UNECE Recommendations, the Report of the Joint Research Center (JRC) on Ecodesign for

Sustainable Products Regulation and other DPP related publications and activities have been analysed in view of a specific relevance for the PV Industry.

Also Multiple marketplaces and industry listings analysed

This analysis is focused on specifications of relevance to define the content of a DPP that refers to a PV Module. It does not include for example an analysis of any technical system environment for the generation or management of a DPP.

The reasoning behind the focus of this analysis on the ESPR and the EN50380 is:

- a) The ESPR is the most actual EU regulation that also includes DPP related stipulations of relevance for the photovoltaic industry. However, with regard to multiple DPP related aspects, many details still are to be defined. Accordingly, the European Commission has been empowered to adopt delegated acts in accordance with ESPR Articles 4 and 72 to supplement this ESPR by setting the respective ecodesign requirements, in particular with regard to any industry specific requirements for DPPs and their content. With the EUBR the EU already provided a more detailed framework and definition of a DPP that, although specifically designed for the battery industry, may serve as a model for other industries, too. Due to the fact that the ESPR has been developed and enacted after the EUBR, it can be assumed that the regulators were aware of and considering the EUBR when they drafted and finalized the ESPR.
- b) With EN50380 there exists a standard for the photovoltaic industry that does not include any stipulations on DPP, but includes many detailed, mandatory as well as best practice marking and documentation requirements to provide for a safe installation, use, and maintenance of PV panels by installers and operators.

In the following sections, some background information on the ESPR as well as the standard EN50380 will be outlined before describing the analysis approach and presenting a suggestion of relevant data for DPP for PV Modules that is based on the analysis of the aforementioned regulations and standards.

3.1 Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation

On May 27, 2024, the The Council of the European Union adopted the ecodesign regulation, which sets requirements for sustainable products. The regulation replaces the existing ecodesign directive and enlarges its scope, beyond energy products, to all kinds of products placed in the EU market, with only a few exceptions (i.e. cars or defense and security related products).

As summarized by the Council, the new regulation introduces new requirements such as product durability, reusability, upgradability and reparability, rules on the presence of substances that inhibit

circularity; energy and resource efficiency; recycled content, remanufacturing and recycling; carbon and environmental footprints; and information requirements, including a Digital Product Passport. The Commission will be empowered to set ecodesign requirements by delegated acts and the industry will have 18 months to comply with them.

Following the Council's approval, once being signed by the President of the European Parliament and the President of the Council, the regulation has been published in the Official Journal of the European Union and entered into force on the 20th day following that of its publication. It will apply from 24 months after the entry into force.

Although the ESPR already provides a very detailed framework and comprehensive set of stipulations about the information a DPP - in principle - can include or be based on, it will be up to the discretion of the European Commission to decide about and adopt the detailed methodologies and which specific information shall be off relevance (within the framework already defined by the ESPR. For example, to define relevant scores, and how aspects can be included or based on relevant and considered by the European Commission, many details are still open and subject to further elaboration and clarification.

When preparing ecodesign requirements, the Commission shall ensure consistency with other Union law and shall take into account:

- a) Union priorities for the climate, the environment, energy efficiency, resource efficiency and security, including a non-toxic circular economy, and other related Union priorities and targets;
- b) relevant Union law, including the extent to which it addresses the relevant product aspects;
- c) relevant international agreements;
- d) self-regulation measures;
- e) relevant national environmental law;
- f) relevant European and international standards;

At the time of the APOLLO Project, when this analysis was done for the first time, no requirements had been published by the Commission yet. Accordingly, the following analysis and suggestions can to a large extent only be based on assumptions, building for example on the European Standard EN 50380:2017-09 as well as on a comparison with the DPP related stipulations of the EU Battery Regulation.

The power to adopt delegated acts referred to in ESPR Article 4, Article 10(1), second subparagraph, Article 11, third paragraph, Article 12(4) and Article 25(3) and (5) shall be conferred on the Commission

for a period of five years from the date of entry into force of this Regulation. The Commission shall draw up a report in respect of the delegation of power not later than nine months before the end of the five-year period. The delegation of power shall be tacitly extended for periods of an identical duration, unless the European Parliament or the Council opposes such extension not later than three months before the end of each period.

In the delegated acts adopted pursuant to ESPR Article 4 paragraph 1, the Commission shall provide economic operators with sufficient time to comply with the ecodesign requirements laid down in those delegated acts, particularly taking into consideration the needs of SMEs, in particular microenterprises. The date of application of a delegated act shall not be earlier than 18 months from its entry into force, except in duly justified cases for the whole act or for some specific requirements, or except in cases of partial repeal or amendment of delegated acts, where an earlier date of application may be set.

The first delegated act to be adopted under this ESPR Article 4 shall not enter into force before the date 12 months from the entry into force of this Regulation.

Meanwhile, the EU Joint Research Center (JRC) has been mandated by the European Commission to study and provide ESPR Work Plan recommendations with potential products and intermediate materials to focus on. This report was published by the JRC in November 2024, with assessments of a number of product groups and horizontal requirements that may be suitable priorities under ESPR. Although the JRC did not recommend PV Modules to be shortlisted as a prioritized product category, key intermediate products were shortlisted with PV relevance, including

- Aluminium, Iron, Steel, Non-ferrous Metal Products
- Glass
- Commodity Chemicals
- Plastics

Table 1: The 11 final products shortlisted by the JRC (Source: JRC own elaboration)

	WATER	AIR	SOIL	BIODIVERSITY	WASTE	CLIMATE CHANGE	ENERGY USE	HUMAN TOXICITY	MATERIAL EFFICIENCY	LIFETIME EXTENSION	STRATEGIC AUTONOMY
Score 42 TEXTILES and FOOTWEAR	5	3	4	4	5	5	5	3	5	3	1
Score 30 FURNITURE	1	3	3	3	4	3	3	2	3	5	1
Score 30 TYRES	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	4
Score 28 BED MATTRESSES	1	3	1	2	5	3	3	2	5	3	1
Score 26 DETERGENTS	4	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	1	1
Score 24 PAINTS	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	1	1
Score 24 COSMETICS	4	2	1	4	3	2	1	2	3	1	1
Score 23 LUBRICANTS	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2
Score 23 TOYS	1	1	1	1	4	2	2	3	3	5	1
Score 21 FISHING GEARS	4	1	1	4	3	2	1	1	3	1	1
Score 19 ABSORBENT HYGIENE PRODUCTS	3	1	2	2	4	2	2	1	1	1	1

Table 2: The 7 intermediate products shortlisted by the JRC (Source: JRC own elaboration)

	WATER	AIR	SOIL	BIODIVERSITY	WASTE	CLIMATE CHANGE	ENERGY USE	HUMAN TOXICITY	STRATEGIC AUTONOMY
Score 30 IRON & STEEL	5	4	2	2	4	5	5	3	5
Score 28 COMMODITY CHEMICALS	4	4	3	3	3	5	4	2	5
Score 27 NON-FERROUS METAL PRODUCTS	3	2	3	2	5	4	5	3	4
Score 26 ALUMINIUM	1	4	4	3	4	4	4	2	3
Score 23 PLASTICS	3	3	2	2	3	4	4	2	3
Score 21 PULP & PAPER	3	2	3	3	2	3	4	1	2
Score 20 GLASS	2	2	2	3	2	4	4	1	3

3.2 European Battery Regulation

On July 10, 2024, the Council of the European Union adopted the regulation concerning batteries and waste batteries, that aims to promote a circular economy by regulating batteries throughout their life cycle.

The regulation therefore establishes end-of-life requirements, including waste collection targets and obligation, targets for the recovery of materials, recycling efficiency targets, mandatory minimum levels of recycled content and extended producer responsibility. This shall be reached through performance, durability and safety criteria, tight restrictions for hazardous substances like mercury, cadmium and lead and mandatory information on the carbon footprint of batteries. Moreover, the regulation introduces labeling and information requirements, among other things on the battery's components and recycled content, and an “electronic battery passport” and a QR code.

This EU Battery Regulation may provide at least some guidance or even serve as a template for DPP’s in other industries, such as for PV modules and the photovoltaic industry.

3.3 European Standard EN 50380:2017-09 and other standards

There are various national, european and international standards that are mandatory or usual practice to be applied when PV Modules are placed on the market, installed or further processed along their life cycle in Europe. Several of them are already addressed in the ESPR. Also there are various standards that directly or indirectly apply to the implementation of DPPs, with 375 of such standards identified by the CIRPASS project in terms of categories like unique identifiers, data carriers, rights and data management, interoperability, data storage, API’s etc. Whereas, in view of the limited resources, and the framework already provided by ESPR, the further analysis in this APOLLO Project is focused on the documentation requirements stipulated in the European Standard EN 50380:2017-09.

Last revised in 2017, at a time when digital product passports were not on the focus of the standard setters yet, the EN 50380:2017-09 describes marking, including nameplate and documentation requirements for non-concentrating photovoltaic modules (in the following also referred to as PV Modules). It includes stipulations about mandatory information that needs to be included in the product documentation or affixed to the product to ensure safe and proper use. Also (not mandatory) best practices are included in this document giving guidance on additional information, for example module’s performance at different irradiance levels.

Markings, including nameplates, are permanently affixed information on the PV Modules, which indelibly states the rating and other information as required by the relevant standard for safe use and

maintenance. While, documentation information is a technical description separate from the photovoltaic module.

Modules shall be supplied with documentation describing the methods of electrical and mechanical installation as well as the electrical ratings of the module. The documentation shall state the Class under which the PV module was qualified and any specific limitations required for that Class. The documentation shall state the environmental conditions to which the module has been qualified. It shall be ensured that appropriate documentation for safe installation, use, and maintenance are available to installers and operators.

The documentation of a PV module typically consists of a user manual and a data-sheet. The user manual/general documentation shall contain all information to comply with national legal product requirements. Extra requirements may apply. Summarized information in addition to the user manual is typically stated in a data-sheet but could also be directly part of the user manual.

For identical PV modules it is considered to be sufficient that one set of documentation is supplied with the PV module shipping unit. International symbols shall be used where applicable.

3.4 Research of Industry Practices and Results of the Analysis

In terms of DPPs, the ESPR provides a very comprehensive framework with some very detailed specifications about what can be included in a DPP. It includes about 100 data points of relevance for a DPP. Moreover, there exist already various standards that shall be considered. However, there are still many stipulations included that give rooms for interpretation, with methodologies and details about the informational requirements to be sorted out. Accordingly, the European Commission has been mandated by the legislators in order to figure out how to fill these gaps and to adopt the respective requirements needed within the next 18 months.

Although the further development of the methodologies and the decisions of the EU Commission must be awaited, this analysis can already try to provide some indication of the informational requirements of the DPP for the photovoltaic industry, in particular by comparing actual standards and other DPP related regulations.

However, in terms of the actual industry practices, when it comes to the sale of PV modules, it becomes obvious that Sellers of used PV Modules and related components parts usually share only key information that is by far not as detailed as what has been outlined in the ESPR. After having analysed numerous marketplaces and adverts for PV modules, and based on insights as well as knowledge gained from discussions with multiple stakeholders, usually, today only very limited data is associated with the adverts/used products, such as

- Product type and other major product info (e.g. used, defect, waste)
- Pictures can include product some details and module label
- Most data points as detailed in ESPR are usually missing

Reflecting the ongoing discussions in politics, industry and society, the industry is pushing for reduction of regulatory burdens. Also, looking at the ongoing political discussion there seems to be kind of a “trend” that the EC and national governments react and try to simplify rules on sustainability. For example, the EC has adopted a new package of proposals to simplify EU rules, boost competitiveness, and unlock additional investment capacity (“Omnibus I and II”). Key elements of these activities include

- Addressing “overlapping, unnecessary or disproportionate rules that are creating unnecessary burden for EU businesses”.
- Addressing the “trickle-down” effect. For example: SMEs (with the exception of listed SMEs) are currently out of the scope of CSRD. However, in practice, many of them are subject to sustainability information requests when they are included in the value chain of larger companies or from financial institutions, such as banks, which fall within the scope of CSRD

3.5 Suggested Data to be included in a DPP for PV Modules

In view of all the research results on the actual regulatory framework, the industry standards and practices as well as the ongoing discussions and political trends, it becomes difficult to suggest a concept for a PV DPP that can meet all the expectations and - at least partly - conflicting interests. Nevertheless, MNS tried to consider and find a balance between the different requirements, needs, interests and expectations that the users of the Minespider Platform and the PV DPP may face.

To achieve this, MNS are suggesting the following the approach:

- a) The Minespider Platform provides flexibility and adaptive tools like templates and a generic framework to generate DPPs. Users can generate DPPs and add information that is available to them. In particular, they can collect and distribute data based on templates and certifications that then can be added or linked with the respective DPP. Instead of adding a fixed format or process for PV DPP with a fixed, mandatory content, MNS propose to develop templates that are designed to meet the requirements for specific use cases. In addition to the already existing templates for the battery industry and the EUBR, MNS can develop and provide templates for example to support ESPR requirements and a separate one for EN50380. Depending on the regulatory developments and any changes in the needs of the users,

individual templates and DPPs can be amended or added and combined or linked with each other.

- b) Since compliance is the main driver for most companies that pushes them to implement DPPs, at least today, MNS suggests to keep the focus first of all on the ESPR when it comes to deciding about the most data points. Accordingly, the table shown in Annex 1 suggests Data for a PV DPP that covers these ESPR requirements. Depending on the further developments this can be amended from time to time, e.g. when the EC provides further guidance and details about the informational requirements and methodologies.
- c) MNS suggests adding to the Minespider Platform the respective options and templates as needed by the PV industry, e.g. to choose the respective products, components or materials from drop box fields or templates.
- d) As long as DPPs or certain content is not mandatory to be provided, it shall be up to the users discretion to decide about the content of the DPP he wants to generate.

3.6 Conclusions

Although the ESPR provides a very comprehensive framework and a detailed outline of the informational requirements for DPPs in general, many details still need to be determined and adopted by the European Commission for the individual industries and product categories. This in particular refers to the following aspects (without claim to completeness):

1. The methodologies that the **scores for durability and recyclability** are to be based on and calculated need to be defined. This in particular requires defining what exactly is meant by and how to measure durability and recyclability of PV Modules.
2. **Vague and indeterminate expressions and phrases** used in the ESPR require definitions and a limited scope that is practical and manageable for the industry and that leads to measurable and comparable results with regard to individual products. This applies, for example, to the interpretation of words or phrases used in the ESPR such as:
 - a. "Indication of real use ..."
 - b. "Ease of ..."
 - c. "Availability of ..."
 - d. "Modularity ..."
 - e. "Compatibility ..."
 - f. "Use of standard [processes] ..."

- g. “Complexity of [processes] ...”
- h. “Specialized [tools] needed ...”
- i. “Design for [recycling] ...”
- j. “Quality of [recycling] ...”
- k. “Use of easily [recyclable] ...”
- l. “Material homogeneity”
- m. “Avoidance of ...”
- n. “Possibility for [high-purity sorting] ...”
- o. “Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to [reuse] ...”
- p. “... needed for proper [use] ...”
- q. “... functional conditions ...”
- r. “... lightweight design ...”
- s. “... other information that could influence sustainable product choices ...”

3. The European Battery Regulation and its interpretation into Digital Battery Passports as proposed by the industry may serve as an illustration of industry practice for an industry specific type of DPP. But - obviously - there are still limits to their transferability to other industries and products.

In the next phase(s) of the APOLLO project, the publications of the European Commission must be awaited. Until then further contributions from industry and other stakeholders can be of relevance and considered, too.

4. Concept Model for the PV DPP

MNS determined the concepts, workflows, and models to collect and share data along the supply chain for dismantling PV Modules, e.g. composition, H&S data, confidentiality aspects, consideration of the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (“ESPR”).

As already mentioned, this project builds on learnings from and standard methodologies already developed in the MINESPIDER Project (Grant Agreement number: 946437), the BATRAW Project (Grant Agreement number: 101058359), as well as the RECIRCULATE Project (Grant Agreement number: 101103972) following EU recommendations. These foundations, in particular the BATRAW as well as the RECIRCULATE project, mainly focused on the automotive industry. Now, with the APOLLO Project, the goal is to extend the focus to the PV industry. In view of the specific needs of the PV industry, the learnings and methodologies have been considered, reasonably adapted and ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for the APOLLO Project (Grant Agreement number: 101122277). Nevertheless, the aim is to provide a platform that enables users to collaborate and share information along multiple supply chains and industries. The consequence is that MNS tries

to design and provide a software environment that is adaptive and flexible and from the data management and usability point of view “agnostic” to the data type of data and industry. Accordingly, MNS identified the data points, needs, and workflows that participants will need to operate a Digital Product Passport (DPP) system that will keep this flexibility, as will be outlined in the following.

4.1 The Minespider Platform

The Minespider Platform, that was developed and designed in the cause of the aforementioned EU funded projects as well as in collaboration with multiple companies, institutions and researchers, has been designed in a way to stay open for any industry, type of product or material and to generate DPPs that can include any type of data. Although in previous projects the main focus was on raw materials and EV batteries the Minespider Platform is capable of and a good basis for being extended to the PV industry.

4.2 The Data Templates

To reflect the informational needs and support the data collection and distribution of the PV industry via the Minespider platform, the design of blockchain-backed data collection templates has been determined.

This includes the following templates / data sets:

- DPP PV component template
- DPP PV Panel - EN 50580 template
- Streaming protocol template

The content of the respective templates is outlined in detail in Annexes 8, 9 and 10 below.

The project partners, as well as any other user of the PV industry registered on the Minespider Platform, can be enabled to make use of these templates in order to collect the information needed by filing the respective template (or by asking the relevant partners to file it).

When a template is filed, a user can generate a certificate based on the respective template, which is encrypted and stored with its hash-code on blockchain to provide an immutable record (to meet the data security needs of the industry).

Such a Minespider Certificate again can be assigned and linked to the respective DPP to circulate the information along the supply chain as needed. This way, for example the informational requirements of the ESPR as well as the standards and expectations of the PV industry can be met.

Figure 1 DPP PV Component Template

The screenshot shows the 'APOLLO - DPP PV Component' template page. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Product passports, Entity certificates, Customers/Suppliers, Access control, Templates (highlighted), and Inventory. Below this are Notifications (98), Minespider - v2.43, and user information for Volker Krümpel (Minespider AG) and English language settings.

The main content area shows the template details for an 'Active' component. The 'Template Details' section includes:

- Name of the Component** (Transparent)
- Title** (Transparent)
- Description**
- Repairability Score** (Transparent)
- Durability Score** (Transparent)
- Carbon Footprint** (Transparent)

 Each score field has a sub-note: 'Repairability Score - If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)' and 'Durability Score - If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)'.

Figure 2 DPP PV Panel - EN 50580 template

The screenshot shows the 'APOLLO - DPP PV Panel - EN 50580' template page. The layout is identical to Figure 1, but the template details are specific to PV panels:

- Product name of the panel** (Transparent)
- Type of panel** (Transparent)
- Panel Identifier** (Transparent)
- Electrical, including wiring, information** (Transparent)

Below the 'Electrical' field, there is a detailed note: 'Extracts from EN50380: Electrical values after stabilization according to the IEC 61215 series shall be verifiable and within the specified rated production tolerances and uncertainties. A procedure is given in Annex B of EN 50380. NOTE 1 Example: Pmax = 250,0 W, rated production tolerance 3 %, binning + 5 W / - 0 W. That means that modules from 250,0 W to 254,9 W are sorted in one bin, rated Pmax = 250,0 W. Tolerance of 3 % results on deviations from 250,0 W from 242,5 W to 257,5 W. If initial values differ by more than the manufacturer's stated production tolerances from stabilized values this shall be stated separately. At the example of an a-Si type module with an initial degradation of 20 % and a rated production tolerance of 5 % for and W0 have to be stated as initial and'.

Figure 3 Streaming Protocol Template

4.3 The PV DPP Concept

Based on the DPP framework provided by the Minespider Platform, the concepts, workflows, and models are provided that enable users to collect and share data along the supply chain by making use of the respective templates and by generating and linking DPPs accordingly. This way, the user can in particular make use of the respective data templates which can be included in the PV DPP as needed. This allows users to generate and share along the products life cycle PV DPPs for example with the relevant data for dismantling PV Modules, e.g. about the composition, H&S data, confidentiality aspects and consideration of the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (“ESPR”).

To be able to operate on the Minespider Platform, and besides the data points referred to in the respective template(s), in particular the following information is of relevance:

- Entity data about the entity that holds the respective user account
- User data, including name and login credentials
- The ID of the respective DPP and the entity the DPP is assigned to.
- An individual QR code that is automatically generated with and assigned to the respective DPP.

- The product or material the respective DPP relates to as well the respective volume or number.

In the following, a short description and visualisation (screenshots) is provided to illustrate the workflow of how a user needs to operate the Minespider Platform to generate a DPP, such as a PV DPP.

In any case, when a DPP is generated on the Minespider Platform, In order to provide for immutability, the Minespider Platform automatically generates an encrypted hash code that is stored on the Minespider blockchain.

4.3.1 Login

In accordance with the usual practice, once a user has registered, he can login with his user credentials and manage his his account, including the entity data the account is associated with.

Figure 4 Login to the Minespider Platform

4.3.2 Dashboard

After login, via the dashboard, the user can see the DPPs he created or received, the DPP Id, the Seller and Recipient, the material or product and the amount assigned to it, the date and the status of the DPP (if it is a draft or has been published), as well as any labels or links associated with the respective DPP.

Moreover the user has the option to generate a new DPP or any entity certificate. This includes the option to make use of the respective templates.

Figure 5 Dashboard for Product Passports

4.3.3 Generating a DPP

When clicking on the “Create Product Passport” button, a workflow is triggered that enables and guides the user to generate a DPP for any kind of product or material.

In the first step, the user can choose the recipient of the DPP. In case the prospective recipient does not have a Minespider Account yet, the user can trigger an invite workflow. Or, in case that he does not want to share the DPP yet, he can choose his own entity as a recipient (and later decide to distribute the DPP).

Figure 6 Generating a DPP

In a next step, the user can define the type of material or product the DPP relates to. At this stage, the user is enabled to refer and link to an existing DPP in order to establish a chain of custody.

With regard to the PV DPP, the user will be enabled to choose a PV Panel as the type of product/material.

Figure 7 Defining the Material or Component the DPP relates to

Figure 8 Define the Type of Material

Figure 9 Define the Type of Product

Figure 10 Option to choose PV Panel

In a next step, the user can add further information to the DPP, such as manufacturer and contact details, product and material related information, information about how to use, repair, recycle the product etc.

At this stage, the user can also make use of the information that was collected via the templates and add certifications or other files accordingly.

Also, for each data point, the user can decide about the level of transparency by choosing if the respective data shall be made public and visible to anyone, or only to the immediate recipient of the DPP, or to everyone who later along the supply chain is linked to the respective DPP in order to provide for the chain of custody.

This concept provides for the flexibility needed by the industry to meet the regulatory requirements as well as the expectations of users who want to not only support transparency, traceability and sustainability but also push the efficiency of the collaboration and exchange of information along complex supply chains.

Figure 11 Add further Information to the PV DPP

The screenshot shows the 'Create product passport' interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with 'Product passports' highlighted. The main area contains five input fields, each with a 'Public' dropdown menu:

- Manufacturer name: Please include the manufacturer name, registered trade name or registered trade mark.
- Manufacturer Postal Address: Please include the manufacturer's postal address details
- Single contact point: Please include details of a single contact point with name and surname
- Web address: Please include web address details
- Email address: Please include the email address (when applicable)

 A 'Proceed' button is located at the bottom right. On the right side, a vertical progress indicator shows four steps:

- Buyer: Get started with finding your recipient.
- Material: Define the information you want to add
- Information: Necessary information for the product passport. (This step is currently active and highlighted in green.)
- Summary: Check all the information if it's correct.

Finally, the system generates a summary of all the data, including an individual QR Code as well as all the data the user added to the DPP and the respective layer of transparency assigned to it. Then it is up to the user to decide if he wants to publish this DPP.

Figure 12 Summary of the DPP

- Product passports
- Entity certificates
- Customers/Suppliers
- Access control
- Templates
- Inventory

- Notifications 97
- Minespider - v2.43
- Minespider AG
- English

Home / Product passports / Product passport detail page

67088c2f

Published

Blockchain Product Passport
67088c2f
Materials: Solar Panel 100 unit

Date
2022-4-21

Solar Panel - 100 (unit)

Owner

SOP manufacturing

[See more](#)

3

Documents

Public details

MSDS:
Attach

- Product passports
- Entity certificates
- Customers/Suppliers
- Access control
- Templates
- Inventory

- Notifications 97
- Minespider - v2.43
- Minespider AG
- English

MSDS:
Attach

Product description:
XYZ

Files attached

Product Specification.pdf

35.26 Kb

Download

EU Certificate of Conformity .pdf

35.26 Kb

Download

Supply Chain Policy.pdf

35.26 Kb

Download

Linked product passports

Frames co.

Published

Buyer:
SOP manufacturing

Materials:
Aluminium frame (200 unit)

Materials in new:
Aluminium frame (200unit)

Gerdau S/A

Published

Buyer:
SOP manufacturing

Materials:
Solar Panel Glass (400 unit)

Materials in new:
Solar Panel Glass (400unit)

MINESPIDER

- Product passports
- Entity certificates
- Customers/Suppliers
- Access control
- Templates
- Inventory

Notifications 97

Minespider - v2.43

Volker Krümpel
Minespider AG

English

Polymer Corp. Germany Published

Buyer:
SOP manufacturing

Materials:
EVA Encapsulating Sheet (600 unit)

Materials in new
EVA Encapsulating Sheet (600unit)

Sender & Buyer information

SOP manufacturing Sender

Address:
Exestrasse 19, 70174, Stuttgart, Germany

Minespider AG Buyer

Address:
Dammstr 16, 6300, Zug, Switzerland

Transparency Layer

Transparency details

ba27784a:
Aluminium frame (200unit)
e94b53c1:
Junction Box (200unit)
87e33c9b:
Solar Panel Glass (400unit)
4fd4f0f6:
EVA Encapsulating Sheet (600unit)

Once a DPP has been generated and based on the referenced other DPPs linked to it, the user can see the history tree with the respective DPPs displayed. This way, the user can follow the chain of custody. By clicking on a DPP displayed in the history tree, the user will be directed to the respective passport and see the information he is authorized to see, in accordance with the level of transparency that has been assigned by its generator/owner and with regard to the individual data points.

Figure 13 The DPP history

5. The Marketplace for Photovoltaics

In order to create a Marketplace for the PV Industry that is backed by the DPPs described above, the user expectations have been investigated and analysed in detail. Also, in order to better understand the actual business practices in online marketplaces for used components, various marketplaces have been analysed. In addition, MNS was able to build on its own experience from the marketplace for EV batteries from the RECIRCULATE project, which is also currently being developed by MNS.

Then, in a second step, the key user stories and concepts have been translated and developed into the designs of the online marketplace (MVP level) for the PV industry. In order to keep the complexity low and to building on DPPs (PV modules and components) as well as related services, the users shall be able to generate and refer to the respective DPPs on the Minespider Platform by linking the individual product listings on the Marketplace with their representing PV DPP on the Minespider Platform.

Accordingly, MNS determined the concepts, workflows and templates of a marketplace for the PV Industry that builds on MNS infrastructure to collect and share data along the supply chains.

Moreover, to support efficient procurement and use, reuse, remanufacture or recycling and dismantling of PV modules and components, the marketplace has been designed in a way that enables users not only to generate and publish listings for product offers, but also for product requests as well

as service offerings and requests. This way, the whole life cycle and all PV related services can be covered by the Marketplace for the PV industry.

As already mentioned, this project builds on learnings from and standard methodologies already developed in other EU funded projects, in particular the RECIRCULATE Project (Grant Agreement number: 101103972). Since the RECIRCULATE project with its battery marketplace mainly focused on the battery industry, now for the APOLLO Project, the goal is to extend the focus to the PV industry. Again, in view of the specific needs of the PV industry, the learnings and methodologies from the battery marketplace designed for the RECIRCULATE project have been considered, reasonably adapted and ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for the APOLLO Project (Grant Agreement number: 101122277).

In the following, the key user stories for the PV centric marketplace are described and visualised.

5.1.1 The Frontpage of the Marketplace for Photovoltaics

The Marketplace for the PV Industry has been designed in a quite simple, straightforward approach. The frontpage is designed to provide the key functionalities of a usual online marketplace that works on the basis of listings: The user shall be enabled to see listings, usually in miniature format, with key information about the individual listing, as well as search and filtering options.

Accordingly, for our PV centric marketplace, the following functionalities are provided on the frontpage: The marketplace includes four categories of listings, including Product Offers, Product Requests, Service Offers, Service Requests

The Individual listings shall provide the key information that is usually expected by the users, including the product or service category, miniature picture, title of the listing, quantity, status, location, pricing information as well as an icon with the option to add the respective listing to a watchlist.

Moreover, the user expects usual functionalities like filtering options, including options to choose the type of listing, select product or service categories, define price ranges and the text to search for. it also include buttons that refer to further pages/functionalities, including a page to show listings in a map view.

The marketplace also provides a header with reference to further pages/functionalities, including a logo and further buttons that when you click on shows details about the page and its focus on reuse, repair, recycling and other battery related services and a button referring to pages to manage user registration, login and help.

And in order to meet the EU grant and regulatory requirements, a footer with reference to further content/pages is provided, including the EU logo and reference to the EU funding, the APOLLO logo and reference to the EU funding, a MINESPIDER logo and reference to “powered by Minespider”, a logo of

further supporting partners of the APOLLO project as well as links to the pages with the imprint, terms of use and privacy policy.

In the following, designs/screenshots are shown that provide a detailed impression of the suggested website. This includes the “tiles” that represent an offer or request. When a user clicks on such a tile, he will be directed to the page to see more details. This can relate to the product offers or requests, to service offers and requests, or to projects or other activities that can be promoted via this marketplace.

The tiles can include a miniature picture or image as well as some key information about the listing, such as the product or service category, the title of the listing, volume, status, location and price.

Figure 14 - Frontpage of the Marketplace for Photovoltaics

5.1.2 Search and Filter Options

A key functionality of a marketplace is to provide the user with options to filter and search through all the listings. Accordingly, there will be multiple, very common options: The user can choose and filter according to the type of listing (product offer, product request, service offer, service request) and he can search and filter by text. Also there are further standard filters options, including filtering by type of product or service, by location or by price range.

5.1.3 The Product Offer Details

When a user clicks on a tile, he is directed to the details of the respective offer. There the user can expect to see the usual information associated with a listing. Besides the information already shown on the “tile”, this can include further images, the state of health and status (original, used, waste etc.) as well as the purpose of the respective product (for reuse, repair, recycling etc.). And the user may see a detailed description of the offer as well as details about the manufacturer, financial details, seller details as well as a location and a map.

A key element of this marketplace where product offers shall be backed by the respective Digital Product Passports (DPPs) is a link to the respective DPP. By clicking on this DPP link the user will be directed to the respective DPP on the Minespider Platform where the user may then get access to the public information.

And, of course, the user has the option to contact the seller, for example to ask questions or initiate a purchase transaction.

Figure 15 - Individual Product Offer Details

Figure 16 - Individual Product Offer Details (further content)

Marketplace for Photovoltaics

test@keinespam.de

to reuse

to repair

to recycle

to service

Manufacturer Details -

Name: DATL
 Details: see www.datl.de

Financial Details -

To be discussed

Seller Details -

Name: Harald Hamilton
 Address: Hauptstraße 3, 97199 Ochsenfurt, Germany
 Email: test@test.com
 Web: none
 Details: Private sale

Location: 97 Würzburg, Germany -

Map Satellite

5.1.4 The Product Requests

A common functionality expected from a market place is to place adverts for product requests. Compared to product offer listings, the content of a listing to request a product includes comparable information, such as the title of the product request, the product category and any details of the requested product, pricing and other financial details as well as details about the requestor and the location. And of course, the request listing provides the functionality to contact the requestor.

Figure 17 - Individual Product Request Details (further content)

Marketplace
for Photovoltaics

test@keinespam.de

to reuse

to repair

to recycle

to service

Product Request
+

PV Panels
—

We are buying used PV Systems for repurposing

max. €7.500,00

| in total

Contact Requestor

Description of the Request
—

Item needed: , for reuse, for repair, for other purposes

Preferred status: original

Seeking used PV modules, mounting systems, inverters and other components to repurpose for in a solar power system. Minimum performance of the PV modules: 75%. Modules produced after 2018 preferred.

Financial Details
—

to be discussed

Requestor Details
—

Name: Power Play GmbH
 Address: Zürich, Switzerland
 Web: [empty]
 Email: volker@keinespam.de
 Details: [empty]

Location: Zürich, Switzerland
—

5.1.5 The Service Offers

Besides product offers and requests, a key element of the marketplace for photovoltaics are the service offers. This enables any service provider to address the PV industry and to market its services. These services can include, for example, transport, analytics, consulting, development, dismantling, repair, reuse, recycling, financing, operation, monitoring and maintenance, repair, repowering, refurbishment of PV installations.

Figure 18 - Service Offers Listings

Figure 19 - Service Offer Details

5.1.6 The Service Requests

Like service offerings, a user can also request services, for example in terms of transport, analytics, consulting, development, dismantling, repair, reuse, recycling, financing, operation, monitoring and maintenance, repair, repowering, refurbishment of PV installations.

Figure 20 - Service Request Listings

The screenshot displays the 'Marketplace for Photovoltaics' interface. At the top right, the user 'test@keinespam.de' is logged in. Navigation buttons include 'to reuse', 'to repair', 'to recycle', and 'to service'. A search bar contains the text 'Service Request' and a filter for '€ 120 - 7500'. The 'Service Requests' section features three cards: 'Deinstallation of 125 PV panels from industrial rooftop' (Remanufacturing), 'PV repair service needed' (Repair), and 'PV Module System Inspection and Maintenance' (Repair). A 'Promoted Activities' sidebar on the right highlights 'The APOLLO Project' as an EU, Swiss, and UK funded project, and 'Retrieval' as an EU funded project.

Figure 21 - Service Request Details

Marketplace
for Photovoltaics

test@keinespam.de

to reuse

to repair

to recycle

to service

Service Request
+

Repair
–

PV repair service needed

Contact Service Requester

Description of the requested service

Or 0.5 MWp pv plant needs to be refurbished/ repaired. We are looking for a repair service option.

Financial Details

To be discussed

Requestor Details

+

Location: Bilbao, Spain

–

5.1.7 Managing the User Account

In accordance with the general practice, a user can manage his user account after registration and login. This includes the following functionalities:

- Manage user and entity details
- Generate new product or service offer or request
- Manage inquiries
- Manage published product or service offers and requests
- Manage drafts of listings that are not published yet.

Figure 22 - Dashboard to manage the User Account

5.1.8 Generating a new Product Listing

To create and manage a new listing item, the user can click on the “Create new item” button to choose the type of listing he wants to create. Then the respective form is shown to provide the details for the new listing.

The content form is now designed according to what is usual practices in terms of used products. In this respect, MNS was first considering mirroring all the data points outlined in the ESPR. However, this would, at least for now, by far go beyond the usual information that is available for the usual person selling a used PV module or other item today. So MNS decided that, at least for now, to keep the form to draft a product item listing in a simplified format that users are quite familiar with today.

Accordingly, the form includes the following “standard” fields:

- Title of the listing (text field)
- Category of the listing (choose from a dropdown list)
- Status of the item (choose from a dropdown list)
- Purpose of the item (choose from a dropdown list)

- Quantity that is offered (numeric field)
- Measurement unit of the quantity (choose from a dropdown list)
- Price in EUR (numeric field)
- Unit that the price relates to (choose from a dropdown list)
- Further financial details (text field)
- Location (text field)
- Minimum health in % (numeric field)
- Description (text field)
- Pictures (upload field)
- Details about the manufacturer of the item
 - Name (text field)
 - Further details (text field)
- Details about the seller of the item
 - Name (text field from user account settings)
 - Address (from user account settings)
 - Email (from user account settings)
 - Website (from user account settings)
 - Further information (from user account settings)

This does not limit the user to still include all the data that is addressed in the ESPR or industry standards like EN50580, in case that this will be or become mandatory. Also the user can make use of the Minespider Platform to generate a PV DPP that includes all the datapoints addressed by the ESPR as well as the EN50580 for example, which then will be linked to the listing generated on the marketplace.

Finally, the user has the option to click on the respective button to either publish the listing, save the listing as a draft or delete the listing.

Figure 23 - Generating a new product offer listing

The screenshot shows a web application interface for a 'Marketplace for Photovoltaics'. On the left, there is a 'My Dashboard' section with links for 'My Inquiries' and 'My Offers', and a card for 'My draft Product Offers: 1' featuring '125 PV Panels from rooftop' with details: 'Volume: 125 units', 'Status: to be checked', 'Location: Berlin, DE', and 'Price: €89 per item'. The main area is a modal form titled 'Add new Product Offer' with a close button (X). The form contains the following fields:

- Title of the product offer:** A text input field with the placeholder 'Type product's title'.
- Product Category:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose an option'.
- Actual Status of the Product:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose an option...'.
- Product Purpose:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose an option...'.
- Quantity:** A text input field with the placeholder 'Type product's quantity'.
- Measurement unit:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose the quantity's measurement unit'.
- Price:** A text input field with the placeholder 'Type product's price'.
- Price Unit:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose the unit the price refers to'.
- Further financial Details:** A text input field with the placeholder 'Provide further financial details'.

At the top right of the dashboard, there is a user profile section with the email 'test@keinespam.de', a 'to service' button, and a 'Create new Item' button. A 'My Account' link is also visible. A 'Built on' logo is present in the bottom right corner of the dashboard area.

Marketplace for Photovoltaic

test@keinespam.de

to service

Seller Details

Name:

Address:

Email:

Website:

Further Information:

Product images (max 3)

Publish Product Offer

Save as draft

Delete

6. Annex - Suggested Data for a PV DPP

TABLE 3: SUGGESTED DATA FOR A PV DPP

1.	Mandatory information according to ESPR	Reasoning	Comments
1.1.	<p>The data to be included in the digital product passport pursuant to ESPR Annex III;</p> <p><i>The requirements related to the digital product passport laid down in the delegated acts adopted pursuant to Article 4 shall specify what data are to or can be included in the digital product passport from among the following elements: [Annex III (a) to (l)]</i></p>	<p>ESPR Article 9(2)(a)</p> <p><i>Where a delegated act contains horizontal ecodesign requirements, point (a) of this paragraph shall not apply.</i></p>	<p><i>Comment MNS: Extracts from Art. 4: The requirements related to the digital product passport laid down in the delegated acts adopted pursuant to ESPR Article 4 shall, as appropriate for the product groups covered, in particular specify the following:</i></p> <p>(a) the data to be included in the digital product passport pursuant to Annex III,</p> <p>(b) one or more data carriers to be used;</p> <p>(c) the layout in which the data carrier is to be presented and its positioning;</p> <p>(d) whether the digital product passport is to be established at model, batch or item level, and the definition of such levels;</p>
1.1.1.	<p><i>information required under [ESPR] Annex III (a), Article 7(2)(b), and Article 7(5) or by other Union law applicable to the relevant product group</i></p>	<p>ESPR Annex III (a)</p>	<p><i>(e) the manner in which the digital product passport is to be made accessible to customers before they are bound by a contract for sale, hire or hire purchase, including in the event of distance selling;</i></p>
1.1.1.1.	<p><i>information on the performance of the product in relation to one or more of the product parameters referred to in Annex I, including a reparability score, a durability score, a carbon footprint or an environmental footprint;</i></p>	<p>ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)</p>	<p>(f) the actors that are to have access to data in the digital product passport and to what data they are to have access;</p> <p>(g) the actors that are to create a digital product passport or update the data in a digital product passport and what data they may introduce or update;</p> <p>(h) the detailed arrangements for introducing or updating data ;</p> <p>(i) the period during which the digital product passport is to remain available,</p> <p>which shall correspond to at least the expected lifetime of a specific product.</p>
1.1.1.1.1.	<p><i>Repairability Score</i></p>	<p>ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)</p>	<p><i>Comment MNS: Methodology to be defined by the EC on the basis of the data in 1.1.1.1.5 ff.</i></p>
1.1.1.1.2.	<p><i>Durability Score</i></p>	<p>ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)</p>	<p><i>Comment MNS: Methodology to be defined by the EC on the basis of the data in 1.1.1.1.4 ff.</i></p>
1.1.1.1.3	<p><i>Carbon Footprint or Environmental Footprint</i></p>	<p>ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)</p>	<p><i>Comment MNS: Methodology to be defined by the EC on the basis of the data in 1.1.1.1.4 ff. and EN Standards</i></p>

1.1.1.1.4.	Durability	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Comment MNS: Methodology to be defined by the EC on the basis of the data in 1.1.1.5 ff. EN Standards that may be of relevance: ISO/IEC 61215 series, ISO/IEC 61730, ISO/IEC 61853 as well as IEC/IEC TS 63126 (Technical Specification)	
1.1.1.1.5.	Reliability		Comment MNS: Methodology to be defined by the EC on the basis of the data in 1.1.1.6 ff. EN Standards that may be of relevance: ISO/IEC 61215 series, ISO/IEC 61730, ISO/IEC 61853 as well as IEC/IEC TS 63126 (Technical Specification)	
1.1.1.1.6.	Guaranteed lifetime		Comment MNS: Not clear what is meant by this. It may, for example, be the mandatory statutory minimum warranty period as stipulated by some EU member states. Or it may be a contractual warranty period that often is granted by manufacturers, importers or resellers. However, these may be subject to various terms and conditions and be difficult to compare.	
1.1.1.1.7.	Technical lifetime		Comment MNS: EN Standards that may be of relevance: ISO/IEC 61215 series, ISO/IEC 61730, ISO/IEC 61853 as well as IEC/IEC TS 63126 (Technical Specification)	
1.1.1.1.8.	Mean time between failures		Comment MNS: EN Standards that may be of relevance: IEC 61709, IEEE 1413, ISO 13849-1,	
1.1.1.1.9.	Indication of real use information on the product		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC	
1.1.1.1.10	Resistance to stresses		Comment MNS: EN Standards that may be of relevance: ISO/IEC 61215 series	
1.1.1.1.11	Ageing mechanisms		Comment MNS: EN Standards that may be of relevance: ISO/IEC 61215 series	
1.1.1.1.12	Ease of repair		ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.13	Ease of maintenance			Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.14	Characteristics of spare parts	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC		
1.1.1.1.15	Availability time of spare parts	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC		
1.1.1.1.16	Affordability of spare parts	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC		

1.1.1.1.17	Modularity		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.18	Compatibility with commonly available tools and spare parts		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.19	Availability of repair and maintenance instructions		
1.1.1.1.20	Number of components used		
1.1.1.1.21	Use of standard components		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.22	Use of component coding standards for the identification of components,		
1.1.1.1.23	Number of processes [in terms of components]		
1.1.1.1.24	Complexity of processes [in terms of components]		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.25	Specialized tools needed [in terms of components]		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.26	Ease of non-destructive disassembly [in terms of components]		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.27	Ease of non-destructive re-assembly, [in terms of components]		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.28	Conditions for access to product data		
1.1.1.1.29	Conditions for access to or use of hardware needed		
1.1.1.1.30	Conditions for access to or use of software needed		
1.1.1.1.31	Ease of upgrading		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.32	Ease of reuse		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.33	Ease of refurbishment		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.34	Number of materials used		

1.1.1.1.35	Use of standard materials		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.36	Use of material coding standards for the identification of materials		
1.1.1.1.37	Number of processes needed [in terms of materials]		
1.1.1.1.38	Complexity of processes needed [in terms of materials]		
1.1.1.1.39	Number of tools needed [in terms of materials]		
1.1.1.1.40	Complexity of tools needed [in terms of materials]		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.41	Ease of nondestructive disassembly [in terms of materials]		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.42	Ease of nondestructive re-assembly [in terms of materials]		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.43	Conditions of access to test protocols,		
1.1.1.1.44	Conditions of access to not commonly available testing equipment,		
1.1.1.1.45	Availability of guarantees specific to remanufactured products		
1.1.1.1.46	Availability of guarantees specific to refurbished products		
1.1.1.1.47	Conditions for access to or use of technologies protected by intellectual property rights		
1.1.1.1.48	Modularity		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.49	Design for recycling	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (d)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.50	Ease of recycling		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.51	Quality of recycling		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC

1.1.1.1.52	<i>Use of easily recyclable materials</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.53	<i>Safe, easy and non-destructive access to recyclable components</i>		<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
1.1.1.1.54	<i>Safe, easy and non-destructive access to recyclable materials</i>		<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
1.1.1.1.55	<i>Safe, easy and non-destructive access to components containing hazardous substances</i>		<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
1.1.1.1.56	<i>Safe, easy and non-destructive access to materials containing hazardous substances</i>		<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
1.1.1.1.57	<i>Material composition</i>		<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
1.1.1.1.58	<i>Material homogeneity</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.59	<i>Possibility for high-purity sorting</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.60	<i>Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to reuse of products and components</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (e)	<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.61	<i>Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to upgrading of products and components</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.62	<i>Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to repair of products and components</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.63	<i>Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to maintenance of products and components</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.64	<i>Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to refurbishment of products and components</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.1.1.65	<i>Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to remanufacturing of products and components</i>		<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>

1.1.1.1.66	Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to recycling of products and components		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.67	Use of substances, and in particular the use of substances of concern, on their own, as constituents of substances or in mixtures, during the production process of products, or leading to their presence in products, including once those products become waste, and their impacts on human health and the environment;	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (f)	
1.1.1.1.68	Use or consumption of energy in one or more life cycle stages of the product, including the effect of physical factors or software and firmware updates on product efficiency and including the impact on deforestation	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(1), Annex I (g)	
1.1.1.1.69	Use or consumption of water in one or more life cycle stages of the product, including the effect of physical factors or software and firmware updates on product efficiency and including the impact on deforestation		
1.1.1.1.70	Use or consumption of other resources in one or more life cycle stages of the product, including the effect of physical factors or software and firmware updates on product efficiency and including the impact on deforestation		
1.1.1.1.71	Use of recycled materials, including critical raw materials	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (h)	
1.1.1.1.72	Content of recycled materials including critical raw materials		

1.1.1.1.73	<i>Recovery of materials, including critical raw materials</i>		
1.1.1.1.74	<i>Use of sustainable renewable materials</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (i)	
1.1.1.1.75	<i>Content of sustainable renewable materials</i>		
1.1.1.1.76	<i>Weight of the product</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (j)	
1.1.1.1.77	<i>Weight of its packaging</i>		
1.1.1.1.78	<i>Product-to-packaging ratio in terms of weight</i>		
1.1.1.1.79	<i>Volume of the product</i>		
1.1.1.1.80	<i>Volume of its packaging</i>		
1.1.1.1.81	<i>Product-to-packaging ratio in terms of volume</i>		
1.1.1.1.82	<i>Incorporation of used components</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (k)	
1.1.1.1.83	<i>Quantity of consumables needed for proper use and maintenance as expressed, inter alia, through yield, technical lifetime, ability to reuse, repair, and remanufacture, mass-resource efficiency, and interoperability;</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (l)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.84	<i>The environmental footprint of the product, expressed as a quantification, in accordance with the applicable delegated act, of a product's life cycle environmental impacts, whether in relation to one or more environmental impact categories or an aggregated set of impact categories;</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (m)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.85	<i>The carbon footprint of the product</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (n)	

1.1.1.1.86	<i>The material footprint of the product</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (o)	
1.1.1.1.87	<i>Microplastic release as expressed through the release during relevant product life cycle stages, including manufacturing, transport, use and end-of-life stages;</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (p)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.88	<i>Nanoplastic release as expressed through the release during relevant product life cycle stages, including manufacturing, transport, use and end-of-life stages;</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.89	<i>Emissions to air released in one or more lifecycle stages of the product as expressed through quantities and nature of emissions, including noise;</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (q)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.90	<i>Emissions to water released in one or more lifecycle stages of the product as expressed through quantities and nature of emissions, including noise;</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.91	<i>Emissions to soil released in one or more lifecycle stages of the product as expressed through quantities and nature of emissions, including noise;</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.92	<i>Amounts of hazardous waste generated</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (r)	
1.1.1.1.93	<i>Amounts of plastic waste generated</i>		
1.1.1.1.94	<i>Amounts of packaging waste generated</i>		
1.1.1.1.95	<i>Amounts of other waste generated</i>		
1.1.1.1.96	<i>Ease of reuse of the amounts of hazardous waste generated</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC

1.1.1.1.97	<i>Ease of reuse of the amounts of plastic waste generated</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.98	<i>Ease of reuse of the amounts of packaging waste generated</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.99	<i>Ease of reuse of the amounts of other waste generated</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.100	<i>Functional performance for use, including as expressed through the ability to perform its intended use, precautions for use, skills required and compatibility with other products or systems</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (s)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.101	<i>functional conditions for use, including as expressed through the ability to perform its intended use, precautions for use, skills required and compatibility with other products or systems</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.102	<i>lightweight design as expressed through reduction of material consumption, load and stress-optimisation of structures, integration of functions within the material or into a single product component, use of lower density or high-strength materials and hybrid materials, with regard to material savings.</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (t)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.103	<i>lightweight design as expressed through reduction of material consumption, load and stress-optimisation of structures, integration of functions within the material or into a single product component, use of lower density or high-strength materials and hybrid</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC

	<i>materials, with regard to waste reduction.</i>		
1.1.1.1.104	<i>lightweight design as expressed through reduction of material consumption, load and stress-optimisation of structures, integration of functions within the material or into a single product component, use of lower density or high-strength materials and hybrid materials, with regard to recycling.</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.1.105	<i>lightweight design as expressed through reduction of material consumption, load and stress-optimisation of structures, integration of functions within the material or into a single product component, use of lower density or high-strength materials and hybrid materials, with regard to other circularity aspects.</i>		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.2.	information for customers and other actors on how to install, use, maintain and repair the product, in order to minimize its impact on the environment and to ensure optimum durability, on how to install third party operating systems where relevant, as well as on collection for refurbishment or remanufacture, and on how to return or handle the product at end-of-life;	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(ii)	
1.1.1.2.1	<i>information for customers and other actors on how to install the product, in order to minimize its impact on the environment and to ensure optimum durability</i>	ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(ii)	Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.
1.1.1.2.2	<i>information for customers and other actors on how to use the product, in order to minimize its impact on the environment and to ensure optimum durability</i>		Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.
1.1.1.2.3	<i>information for customers and other actors on how to maintain the product, in order to minimize its impact on the environment and to ensure optimum durability</i>		Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.

1.1.1.2.4	<i>information for customers and other actors on how to repair the product, in order to minimize its impact on the environment and to ensure optimum durability</i>			Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.
1.1.1.2.5	<i>information for customers and other actors on how to install third party operating systems where relevant</i>			
1.1.1.2.6	<i>information for customers and other actors on collection for refurbishment or remanufacture</i>			
1.1.1.2.7	<i>information for customers and other actors on how to return or handle the product at end-of-life;</i>			
1.1.1.3.	information for treatment facilities on disassembly, reuse, refurbishment, recycling, or disposal at end-of-life;	ESPR	Article 7(2)(b)(iii)	
1.1.1.3.1.	<i>information for treatment facilities on disassembly</i>	ESPR	Article 7(2)(b)(iii)	
1.1.1.3.2	<i>information for treatment facilities on reuse,</i>			
1.1.1.3.3	<i>information for treatment facilities on refurbishment,</i>			
1.1.1.3.4	<i>information for treatment facilities on recycling</i>			
1.1.1.3.5	<i>information for treatment facilities on disposal at end-of-life;</i>			
1.1.1.4.	other information that could influence sustainable product choices for customers and the way the product is handled by parties other than the manufacturer in order to facilitate appropriate use, value-retaining operations and correct treatment at end-of-life;	ESPR	Article 7(2)(b)(iv)	
1.1.1.4.1.	<i>other information that could influence sustainable product choices for customers and the way the product is handled by parties other than the manufacturer in order to facilitate appropriate use</i>	ESPR	Article 7(2)(b)(iv)	Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.4.2	<i>other information that could influence sustainable product choices for customers and the way the product is handled by parties other than the manufacturer in order to facilitate appropriate value-retaining operations</i>			Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC

1.1.1.4.3	other information that could influence sustainable product choices for customers and the way the product is handled by parties other than the manufacturer in order to facilitate correct treatment at end-of-life;		Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC
1.1.1.5	Unless otherwise provided for under paragraph 6, point (b), the information requirements shall make it possible to track the substances of concern, throughout the life cycle of the products concerned, unless such tracking is already possible pursuant to information requirements laid down in another delegated act adopted pursuant to Article 4 covering the products concerned, and shall include at least the following:	ESPR Article 7(5)	
1.1.1.5.1	the name or numerical code of the substances of concern present in the product, as follows:	ESPR Article 7(5)(a)	
1.1.1.5.1.1	name in the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) nomenclature, or another international name when IUPAC name is not available	ESPR Article 7(5)(a)(i)	
1.1.1.5.1.2	other names, including usual name, trade name, abbreviation	ESPR Article 7(5)(a)(ii)	
1.1.1.5.1.3	European Community (EC) number, as indicated in the European Inventory of Existing Commercial Chemical Substances (EINECS), the European List of Notified Chemical Substances (ELINCS) or the No Longer Polymer (NLP) list or the number assigned by the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), if available and appropriate;	ESPR Article 7(5)(a)(iii)	
1.1.1.5.1.4	the Chemical Abstract Service (CAS) name and number, if available;	ESPR Article 7(5)(a)(iv)	
1.1.1.5.1.5	the location of the substances of concern within the product;	ESPR Article 7(5)(b)	
1.1.1.5.1.6	the concentration, maximum concentration or concentration range of the substances of concern, at the level of the product, its relevant components, or spare parts	ESPR Article 7(5)(c)	
1.1.1.5.1.7	relevant instructions for the safe use of the product	ESPR Article 7(5)(d)	

1.1.1.5.1.8	<i>information relevant for disassembly, preparation for reuse, reuse, recycling and the environmentally sound management of the product at end-of-life.</i>	ESPR Article 7(5)(e)	
1.1.1.5.2	<i>other Union law applicable to the relevant product group</i>	other Union law applicable to the relevant product group	<i>Comment MNS: clarification needed from the EC</i>
1.1.2.	<i>The unique product identifier at the level indicated in the applicable delegated act adopted pursuant to Article 4;</i>	ESPR Annex III (b)	
1.1.3.	<i>the Global Trade Identification Number as provided for in International Organization for Standardisation/International Electrotechnical Commission standard ISO/IEC 15459-6 or equivalent of products or their parts;</i>	ESPR Annex III (c)	
1.1.4	<i>relevant commodity codes, such as a TARIC code as defined in Regulation (EEC) No 2658/87</i>	ESPR Annex III (d)	
1.1.5.	<i>compliance documentation and information required under this Regulation or other Union law applicable to the product, such as the declaration of conformity, technical documentation or conformity certificates</i>	ESPR Annex III (e)	
1.1.6	<i>user manuals, instructions, warnings or safety information, as required by other Union law applicable to the product</i>	ESPR Annex III (f)	<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
1.1.7	<i>information related to the manufacturer, such as its unique operator identifier and the information referred to in Article 27(7);</i>	ESPR Annex III (g)	<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from Annex III: The unique operator identifiers referred to in point (g), shall, where relevant for the products concerned, comply with standards # ISO/IEC 15459-1:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-2:2015, ISO/IEC 15459-3:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-4:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-5:2014 and ISO/IEC 15459-6:2014.</i>

1.1.8	<i>unique operator identifiers other than that of the manufacturer</i>	ESPR Annex III (h)	<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from Annex III: The unique operator identifiers referred to in point (h) shall, where relevant for the products concerned, comply with standards ISO/IEC 15459-1:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-2:2015, ISO/IEC 15459-3:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-4:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-5:2014 and ISO/IEC 15459-6:2014.</i>
1.1.9	<i>unique facility identifiers;</i>	ESPR Annex III (i)	<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from Annex III: The unique facility identifiers referred to in point (i) shall, where relevant for the products concerned, comply with standards ISO/IEC 15459-1:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-2:2015, ISO/IEC 15459-3:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-4:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-5:2014 and ISO/IEC 15459-6:2014.</i>
1.1.10	<i>information related to the importer, including the information referred to in Article 29(3) and its Economic Operators Registration and Identification (EORI) number;</i>	ESPR Annex III (j)	
1.1.11	<i>the name, contact details and unique operator identifier of the economic operator established in the Union responsible for carrying out the tasks set out in Article 4 of Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 or Article 15 of Regulation (EU) 2023/988, or similar tasks pursuant to other Union law applicable to the product;</i>	ESPR Annex III (k)	<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from Annex III: The unique operator identifiers referred to in point (k) shall, where relevant for the products concerned, comply with standards ISO/IEC 15459-1:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-2:2015, ISO/IEC 15459-3:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-4:2014, ISO/IEC 15459-5:2014 and ISO/IEC 15459-6:2014.</i>
1.1.12	<i>the reference of the digital product passport service provider hosting the back-up copy of the digital product passport</i>	ESPR Annex III (l)	
2.	Voluntary Information according to ESPR		

2.1	<i>The delegated acts adopted pursuant to Article 4 shall identify information relevant to ecodesign requirements that manufacturers may include in the digital product passport in addition to the information required pursuant to [ERSP] Article 9(2), point (a), including information on specific voluntary labels applicable to the product. That shall include whether an EU Ecolabel has been awarded to the product in line with Regulation (EC) No 66/2010.</i>	ESPR Annex III last paragraph	
3.	Information related to EN 50580		
3.2.	Mandatory Information		
3.2.1	Electrical, including wiring, information	EN 50580	
3.2.1.1	polarity of terminals or leads		
3.2.1.2	"Maximum system voltage" (V_{sys})		
3.2.1.3	Maximum overcurrent protection (OCP) rating		<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50580: Overcurrent protection devices with a 1hr, 1.35 /_R overload rating, where /_R is the rated value of the overcurrent protection device, are recommended.</i> <i>NOTE Compliance can be checked according to EN 61730-2 MST 26. /_R-rating can be determined using procedure in Annex A to EN 50380.</i>
3.2.1.4	Class of protection against electrical shock, in accordance with EN 61730-1		<i>Comment MNS: see further details in 5.2.3 f) EN 50380</i>
3.2.1.5	Voltage at open-circuit (V_{OC})		<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380: The following electrical data shall be shown as relative to standard test conditions (1 000 W/m², 25 °C, AM 1,5G according to CLC/TS 61836) and after stabilization. Manufacturer's stated rated production tolerance shall be given also under standard test conditions (STC).</i>
3.2.1.6	Voltages at maximum power point including rated production tolerance (V_{Pmax})		

3.2.1.7	Current at maximum power point including rated production tolerance (I_{Pmax})		
3.2.1.8	PV module maximum power including rated production tolerance (P_{max})		
3.2.1.9	Current at short-circuit including rated production tolerance (I_{sc})		
			<p><i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i></p> <p>Electrical values after stabilization according to the IEC 61215 series shall be verifiable and within the specified rated production tolerances and uncertainties. A procedure is given in Annex B of EN 50380.</p> <p>NOTE 1 Example: Pmax = 250,0 W, rated production tolerance 3 %, binning + 5 W / - 0 W. That means that modules from 250,0 W to 254,9 W are sorted in one bin, rated Pmax = 250,0 W. Tolerance of 3 % results on deviations from 250,0 W from 242,5 W to 257,5 W.</p> <p>If initial values differ by more than the manufacturer's stated production tolerances from stabilized values this shall be stated separately.</p> <p>At the example of an a-Si type module with an initial degradation of 20 % and a rated production tolerance of 5 %, Isc and Voc have to be stated as initial and stabilized parameters.</p>

			If output of module (I_{sc} , V_{oc} and P_{max}) is site or mounting means dependent (e.g. due to back side illumination of bifacial cells) variability and maximal output (I_{sc} , V_{oc} and P_{max}) shall be stated.
3.2.1.10	Relative temperature coefficients in [%/K] for I_{sc} , P_{max} and V_{oc} at STC		<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i> The values for I_{MPP} and V_{MPP} can be provided.
3.2.1.11	State if temperature coefficients are linear. In cases of nonlinear temperature coefficients according to EN 60904-10 further information regarding temperature coefficients shall be provided.		
3.2.1.12			<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i> The electrical documentation shall include a detailed description of the electrical installation wiring method to be used. This description shall include:
3.2.1.13	The minimum cable diameters for PV modules intended for field wiring		
3.2.1.14	Any limitations on wiring methods and wire management that apply to the junction box for the PV module		
3.2.1.15	The size, type, material, and temperature rating of the conductors to be used		
3.2.1.16	Type of terminals for field wiring		
3.2.1.17	Specific PV connector model/types and manufacturer to which the PV module connectors can be mated		
3.2.1.18	The bonding method(s) to be used (if applicable) shall be specified. All provided or specified hardware shall be identified in the documentation		

3.2.1.19	All provided or specified hardware shall be identified in the documentation		
3.2.1.20	A statement if protective devices (e.g. bypass diode etc.) are part of the PV module.		
3.2.1.21	A statement if the protective device is replaceable		

<p>3.2.1.22</p>	<p>To facilitate proper system sizing the manufacturer shall include relevant parameters in the documentation that allow system layout based not only on STC values given in the documentation.</p>	<p><i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i></p> <p>For example, a safety factor for Voc and Isc of 1,25 is recommended since irradiance is often higher than 1 000 W/m² and temperature below 25 °C may raise Voc.</p> <p>The following or equivalent statement shall be included:</p> <p>“Under normal conditions, a photovoltaic module is likely to experience conditions that produce higher current and/or voltage than reported at standard test conditions. Accordingly, the values of Isc and Voc marked on this PV module should be multiplied by a factor of 1,25 when determining component voltage ratings, conductor current ratings, and size of controls (e.g. inverter) connected to the PV output.”</p> <p>The safety factor of 1,25 for the minimum voltage rating of the components can be modified during the design of a system according to the minimum temperature of the location of the installation and the temperature coefficient for Voc. Isc can be adjusted based on maximal temperature, irradiance and orientation of the module. To this end a full simulation for the specific location is required using long term weather data.</p> <p>A statement indicating the maximum altitude the PV module is designed for. Electrical de-ratings applied in</p>
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			accordance to EN 61730-1. Voltage de-rating as specified in the insulation coordination can be applied.
3.2.2	Mechanical information		
3.2.2.1	A statement indicating the design load for each mounting method (clamps, bolts, etc.) for securing the module.		
3.2.2.2	Limitations for each mounting method (slope, mounting means, air gap between structure and module, rack mounting, roof or building integrated / attached, etc.)		
3.2.2.3	Limitations for each mounting method if fire rating is dependent on mounting method.		
3.2.3.	Installation information		
3.2.3.1	Assembly information and instructions shall be provided with a product shipped in subassemblies, and shall be detailed and adequate to the degree required to facilitate complete and safe assembly of the product.		<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
3.2.3.2	The documentation shall include a statement advising that external or otherwise artificially concentrated sunlight shall not be directed onto the front or back face of the PV module (if not qualified for		
3.2.3.4	Mounting position (e.g. holes or position of clamps). Details for mounting are given in 4.3.3. of EN 50380		
3.2.3.5	Equipotential bonding position		
3.2.3.6	Weight (kg)		

3.2.3.7	All relevant certificates (according to EN 45011) for safe installation and use shall be listed in the documentation.		<i>Comment MNS: Relevant EN standard: ISO/IEC 50380 (see below Point 3 ff.)</i>
3.3.	Best practice Information		
3.3.1	Electrical, including wiring, information		
3.3.1.1	Nominal module operating temperature – NMOT		
3.3.1.2	Performance at NMOT (MQT 06.2).		
3.3.1.3	Performance at low irradiance (MQT 07)		
3.3.1.4	Relative temperature coefficients in [%/K] for I _{sc} , P _{max} and V _{oc} at 200 W/m ² or others irradiance levels.		<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380: NOTE The values for IMPP and VMPP can be provided.</i>
3.3.1.5	The number of maximum series and parallel PV module in a string configurations.		
3.3.1.6	Information as per EN 50380 Annex C for energy yield calculation.		
3.3.1.7	Information on module insulation behaviour as function of environment as per EN 50380 C.3.		
3.3.1.8	Information of PV modules capacitance as per EN 50380 C.4.		
3.3.2.	Installation information – Constructive characteristics		
3.3.2.1	Technical drawing with number of cells and bypass diode (type and ratings) circuit as applicable		
3.3.2.2	outer dimensions (length, width) of the photovoltaic module		
3.3.2.3	total thickness of the photovoltaic module (including frame and junction box)		
3.3.2.4	frame material		

3.3.2.5	kind of substrate and superstrate		
3.3.2.6	junction box in accordance to EN 62790		
3.3.2.7	module cable in accordance to EN 50618 (future IEC 62930 ED1)		
3.3.2.8	connector in accordance to EN 62852 and its IP protection in accordance to EN 60529.		
3.3.3.	Certification		
3.3.3.1	All additional certificates (according to EN 45011) can be listed in the documentation.		
3.3.4	Other Information		
3.3.4.1	Number, technology and material of photovoltaic cells		
3.3.4.1.1	State number of cells in series and any parallel internal wiring		
3.3.4.1.2	State cell technology and material.		<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i> NOTE E.g. mono-crystalline Si, poly-crystalline Si, n-type Si, UMG-Si, backside-contacted, bifacial, CIGS, a-Si, μ -Si, npn-type, pnp-type, CdTe, etc.
3.3.4.2	Fire classification		
3.3.4.2.1	A statement indicating the fire classification (EN 13501-1)		
3.3.4.2.2	details of the specific parameter(s) when the fire classification is dependent on a specific mounting structure, specific spacing, or specific means of attachment to the roof or structure.		<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i> NOTE National requirements may apply.
3.4.	Marking information		
3.4.1	Module identification		

3.4.1.1	Each module shall have the following clear and indelible markings		
3.4.1.2	Name, registered trade name or registered trade mark of manufacturer;		
3.4.1.3	type or model number designation		
3.4.1.4	serial number		
3.4.1.5	date and place of manufacture; alternatively serial number allowing to trace the date and place of manufacture		
3.4.2.	Electrical information		
3.4.2.1	Polarity of terminals or leads;		
3.4.2.2	PV connectors shall be clearly marked indicating the terminal polarity.		
3.4.2.3	PV connectors shall be marked with a symbol “Do not disconnect under load”, as given in EN 61730-1:2016, Annex A (e.g. graphical symbol IEC 60417-6070). Symbol or warning notice shall be imprinted or marked close to connector.		
3.4.2.4	Maximum overcurrent protection rating (see EN 50380 4.3.2 c));		
3.4.2.5	“Maximum system voltage” or V_{sys} ;		
3.4.2.6	Class of protection against electrical shock, in accordance to EN 61730-1		<p><i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i></p> <p>For Class II and Class 0 PV modules, the graphical symbol IEC 60417-6042: Caution, risk of electric shock, shall be applied near the PV module electrical connection means.</p> <p>PV modules shall be marked to indicate the classes as follows:</p>

	PV module Classification	Marking	Symbol
	Class II	Marking according to IEC 60417–5172: Class II equipment	
	Class 0	no marking	no symbol
	Class III	Marking according to IEC 60417–5180: Class III equipment	
3.4.2.7	PV modules provided with a functional earth connection shall be marked with the graphical symbol IEC 60417-5018: Functional earthing. 		
3.4.2.8	PV modules provided with terminals for field wiring rated only for use with copper wire shall be marked, at or adjacent to the terminals, with the statement “Use copper wire only”, “Cu only”, or the equivalent.		
3.4.2.9	PV modules provided with terminals for field wiring rated only for use with a different specific wiring material shall be marked with a similar statement referring to the rated material.		
			<i>Comment MNS: Extracts from EN50380:</i> The following electrical data shall be shown as relative to standard test conditions (1 000 W/m ² , 25 °C, AM 1,5G according to CLC/TS 61836). Manufacturer’s stated tolerance shall be given under standard test conditions (STC):

3.4.2.10	“Voltage at open-circuit” or “ V_{oc} ” including rated production tolerances		
3.4.2.11	“Voltages at maximum power point” or “ V_{pmax} ” including rated production tolerances		
3.4.2.12	“Current at maximum power point”; or “ I_{pmax} ” including rated production tolerances		
3.4.2.13	“PV module maximum power” or “ P_{max} ” including rated production tolerances;		
3.4.2.14	“Current at short-circuit”; or “ I_{sc} ” including rated production tolerances.		
3.4.2.15	Module with open circuit voltage exceeding 35 V and/or with highest system voltage exceeding 35 V shall have a warning sign regarding the hazard of electric shock in proximity to the means of connection (e.g. on cable near PV connector).		
3.5	Certificates and certification body marks:		
3.5.1	Certification body mark can be applied to the module, if permission granted by certification body		
3.5.2	Applicable and passed standards for PV module		
3.6.	Other information		

7. Annex - PV DPP Component Template

TABLE 4: SUGGESTED PV DPP COMPONENT TEMPLATE

Number	Data Point	Comment	Level
1	Name of the Component	Name of the component or product (according to product specification)	Transparent
2	Title	Description	Transparent
3	Repairability Score	Repairability Score – if applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)	Transparent
4	Durability Score	Durability Score – if applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)	Transparent
5	Carbon Footprint	Carbon Footprint – if applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)	Transparent
6	Environmental Footprint	Environmental Footprint – if applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i)	Transparent
7	Durability	Durability – if applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent
8	Conditions for access to or use of hardware needed	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
9	Conditions for access to or use of software needed	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent

10	Complexity of processes [in terms of components]	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
11	Specialized tools needed [in terms of components]	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
12	Ease of non-destructive disassembly [in terms of components]	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
13	Ease of non-destructive re-assembly [in terms of components]	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
14	Conditions for access to product data	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
15	Modularity	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
16	Compatibility with commonly available tools and spare parts	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
17	Availability of repair and maintenance instruction	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
18	Number of components used	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
19	Use of standard components	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent

20	Number of processes [in terms of components]	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
21	Ageing mechanisms	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent
22	Ease of repair	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
23	Ease of maintenance	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
24	Characteristics of spare parts	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
25	Availability time of spare parts	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
26	Affordability of spare parts	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (b)	Transparent
27	Reliability	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent
28	Guaranteed lifetime	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent
29	Technical lifetime	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent
30	Mean time between failures	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent

31	Indication of real use information on the product	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent
32	Resistance to stresses	If applicable as specified according to ESPR Article 7(2)(b)(i), Annex I (a)	Transparent

8. Annex - PV DPP Panel EN50580 Template

TABLE 5: SUGGESTED PV DPP EN50580 TEMPLATE

Number	Data Point	Comment	Level
1	Product name of the panel	Name of the panel, batch or series	Transparent
2	Type of panel	Type of panel	Transparent
3	Panel Identifier	Serial number (for group or individual panel(s))	Transparent
4	Electrical, including wiring, information	Detailed description of electrical values, tolerances, degradation, and site-specific parameters	Transparent
5	Polarity of terminals or leads	Polarity of terminals or leads	Transparent
6	Maximum system voltage (V _{sys})	Maximum system voltage	Transparent
7	Maximum overcurrent protection (OCP) rating	Based on EN50580 1hr, 1.35/R rating recommendation	Transparent
8	Class of protection against electrical shock	Class rating and further info per EN 50380 5.2.3 f)	Transparent
9	Voltage at open-circuit (VOC)	Rated values under standard test conditions (STC)	Transparent

10	Voltages at maximum power point	Rated values under standard test conditions (STC)	Transparent
11	Current at maximum power point	Rated values under standard test conditions (STC)	Transparent
12	PV module maximum power	Rated values under standard test conditions (STC)	Transparent
13	Current at short-circuit	Rated values under standard test conditions (STC)	Transparent
14	Relative temperature coefficients	Values for IMPP and VMPP	Transparent
15	State if temperature coefficients are linear	If nonlinear, provide further information per EN 60904-10	Transparent
16	Electrical documentation	Includes detailed wiring description and methods	Transparent
17	Minimum cable diameters	For field wiring of PV modules	Transparent
18	Wiring method limitations	For junction box management	Transparent
19	Size/type/material/rating of conductors	Details to be provided	Transparent
20	Type of terminals for field wiring	Description of the terminal types	Transparent
21	Specific PV connector types	Connector types and manufacturers	Transparent
22	Bonding methods used	Specify hardware and bonding techniques	Transparent

23	Hardware identification	All provided/specified hardware must be identified	Transparent
24	Protective device statement	If bypass diode or other protective device exists	Transparent
25	Replaceability of protective device	State whether replaceable	Transparent
26	System sizing safety factor	Voc/Isc x 1.25 recommended, full explanation and design requirements	Transparent
27	Mechanical information	Mechanical details of the module	Transparent
28	Design load statement	Clamps, bolts, etc. for securing module	Transparent
29	Mounting limitations	For slope, structure, roof integration, etc.	Transparent
30	Fire-rating dependent mounting limitation	State if method affects fire rating	Transparent
31	Installation information	Installation-specific details	Transparent
32	Assembly standard	Refer to ISO/IEC 50380	Transparent
33	Sunlight exposure caution	External/concentrated sunlight not allowed unless qualified	Transparent
34	Mounting position	Mounting clamp holes or positions	Transparent
35	Equipotential bonding	Bonding position information	Transparent
36	Weight (kg)	Total module weight	Transparent
37	Max. series and parallel module numbers	For string configurations	Transparent

38	Energy yield info (EN 50380 Annex C)	Details for energy calculation	Transparent
39	Module insulation behavior	Function of environment (per EN 50380 C.3)	Transparent
40	Module capacitance	As per EN 50380 C.4	Transparent
41	Installation information — constructive	Constructive characteristics	Transparent
42	Outer dimensions	Length and width of the module	Transparent
43	Total thickness	Incl. frame and junction box	Transparent
44	Frame material	Frame material	Transparent
45	Substrate and superstrate type	Substrate and superstrate types	Transparent
46	Junction box EN 62790	Junction box standard	Transparent
47	Module cable EN 50618	Cable specification	Transparent
48	Connector EN 62852	Connector and IP standard	Transparent
49	Other information	Cell count, material, structure	Transparent
50	Cell wiring in series/parallel	Series/parallel configuration	Transparent
51	Cell technology and material	e.g. mono-Si, poly-Si, n-type	Transparent
52	Fire classification	Fire classification	Transparent
53	Fire classification statement	Fire class per EN 13501-1	Transparent
54	Fire parameter specification	When classification applies	Transparent

55	Marking information	Labeling and compliance marks	Transparent
56	Module identification	Identification requirements	Transparent
57	Required module markings	Clear, indelible markings required	Transparent
58	Trade name	Manufacturer's trade name or mark	Transparent
59	Model/type number	Module type designation	Transparent
60	Serial number	Unique identifier	Transparent
61	Date/place of manufacture or traceable ID	For traceability	Transparent
62	Electrical information (label)	Key electrical data	Transparent
63	Electrical information	Electrical information	Transparent
64	Polarity of terminals or leads	Polarity of terminals or leads	Transparent
65	PV connectors shall be clearly marked indicating the terminal polarity	PV connectors shall be clearly marked indicating the terminal polarity.	Transparent
66	PV connectors shall be marked with a symbol 'Do not disconnect under load'	As given in EN 61730-1:2016, Annex A (e.g. IEC 60417-6070). Symbol or warning notice shall be imprinted or marked close to connector.	Transparent
67	Maximum overcurrent protection rating	See EN 50380 4.3.2 c)	Transparent
68	Maximum system voltage or V _{sys}	Maximum system voltage	Transparent

69	Class of protection against electrical shock	For Class II and Class 0 PV modules, IEC 60417-6042 symbol and markings per EN50380	Transparent
70	PV modules provided with a functional earth connection	Marked with IEC 60417-5018: Functional earthing symbol	Transparent
71	PV modules provided with terminals for field wiring - Cu only	Marked with statement 'Use copper wire only', 'Cu only', or the equivalent	Transparent
72	PV modules provided with terminals for field wiring - specific material	Marked with rated material if not copper	Transparent
73	The following electrical data shall be shown as relative to STC	1000 W/m ² , 25 °C, AM 1.5G according to CLC/TS 61836. Manufacturer's stated tolerance under STC	Transparent
74	Voltage at open-circuit or Voc	Includes rated production tolerances	Transparent
75	Voltages at maximum power point or Vpmax	Includes rated production tolerances	Transparent
76	Current at maximum power point or Ipmax	Includes rated production tolerances	Transparent
77	PV module maximum power or Pmax	Includes rated production tolerances	Transparent
78	Current at short-circuit or Isc	Includes rated production tolerances	Transparent
79	Module with open circuit voltage exceeding 35V	Warning sign for electric shock near connector required	Transparent

80	Certificates and certification body marks	Certificates and certification body marks	Transparent
81	Certification body mark can be applied to the module	If permission granted by certification body	Transparent
82	Applicable and passed standards for PV module	Applicable and passed standards for PV module	Transparent
83	Other information	Other information	Transparent

9. Streaming Protocol Template

TABLE 6: SUGGESTED STREAMING PROTOCOL TEMPLATE

Number	Data Point	Comment	Level
1	Panel Reference	Panel ID given by the Apollo project	Public
2	Producer	Manufacturer of the PV panel	Transparent
3	Installed location	Location where the panel was installed	Transparent
4	Installed time (years)	Number of years installed	Transparent
5	Module type	Module type according to the information provided by the manufacturer	Transparent
6	Serial Number of the Panel	Panel serial number	Transparent
7	Date of production of the panel	Year / date when the panel has been produced	Transparent

8	Maximum power (Wp)	Maximum power output of the panel in Wp	Transparent
9	Weight of the panel (kg)	Weight of the panel in kg	Transparent
10	Width of the panel	Width of the panel	Transparent
11	Length of the panel	Length of the panel	Transparent
12	Hight of the panel	Hight of the panel	Transparent
13	Frame material	Material the frame is made of	Transparent
	– Aluminium alloys		
	– Polymeric		
	– Other		
14	Assembling type	The method the frame is assembled	Transparent
	– Glued		
	– Screwed		
	– Soldered		
	– Other		
15	Al-frame (measured) (kg)	Al-frame (measured) / kg	Transparent
16	Frame condition	Condition of the frame	Transparent

	– Good		
	– Average		
	– Bad		
17	Full frame weight (calculated) / kg	Full frame weight (calculated) / kg	Transparent
18	Junction box material	Junction box material	Transparent
	– Polymer		
	– Other		
19	Junction box + Connectors (weight measured) (kg)	Junction box and Connectors (measured) weight in kg	Transparent
20	Cable (measured) (kg)	Cable (measured) in kg	Transparent
21	PV laminate weight (kg)	PV laminate weight in kg	Transparent
22	Total cell number	60; 72; 120; 144; or other	Transparent
23	Arrangement of cells	6×10; 6×12; 6×20; 6×24; or other	Transparent
24	Cell type	Choose the type of cell	Transparent
	– Monocrystalline		
	– Polycrystalline		

	– Other		
25	Cell geometry	Choose the cell geometry	Transparent
	– Full		
	– Full-half		
	– Other		
26	Cell dimensions (mm ²)	Cell dimensions in mm ²	Transparent
27	Wafer thickness (µm)	Wafer thickness in µm	Transparent
28	Silicium / Si contained (kg)	Silicium / Si contained (kg)	Transparent
29	Number of busbars	Number of busbars	Transparent
30	Copper / Cu contained (kg)	Copper / Cu contained in the cell (kg)	Transparent
31	Silver / Ag in contact width (mm)	Silver / Ag in contact width (mm)	Transparent
32	Silver / Ag content (%)	Silver / Ag - content in %	Transparent
33	Glass thickness (mm)	Glass thickness (mm)	Transparent
34	Glass weight (kg)	Glass weight (kg)	Transparent
35	Antimon / Sb - content (%)	Antimon / Sb-content (%)	Transparent

36	Backsheet polymer	Type of polymer	Transparent
37	Backsheet thickness (µm)	Backsheet thickness (µm)	Transparent
38	Backsheet weight (kg)	Backsheet weight (kg)	Transparent
39	Fluor contained (yes/no)	Fluor contained	Transparent
40	EVA width (µm)	EVA width (µm)	Transparent
41	EVA weight (kg)	EVA weight (kg)	Transparent
42	Backsheet critical temperature (°C)	Backsheet critical temperature (°C)	Transparent
43	EVA critical temperature (°C)	EVA critical temperature (°C)	Transparent
44	Title	Description	Transparent
45	Further comments	Any comment or other note can be added here	Transparent